

A STUDY OF RURAL TELECOM DISTRIBUTION (GSM) AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER MARKET SHARE (CMS)

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify the factors influencing the Telecommunication distribution efficiency in rural area specific to Rajasthan region through exploring and studying the nature of rural GSM telecom business. It investigates the factors impacting the Customer Market Share (CMS) of prepaid business in rural towns with high geographical spread. The research constructs were developed based on the Hub and Spoke model of distribution and incorporated the new factors, which is constituted by Covered population, Mobility penetration, Network traffic and town distance from the base distributor town. Regression analysis was employed to study the relationship. The results show that there is an impact of these additional factors on CMS. Based on these factors, this research paper suggests a modified model which is 'Retailer as Distributor' (RAD) model in the towns to improve the distribution efficiency in rural towns.

Keywords; Rural Telecom Distribution, Customer Market Share (CMS), Hub & Spoke model, Retailer as Distributor (RAD)

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INTRODUCTION

The Telecom Industry

The Indian telecommunications industry has witnessed tremendous growth over the last few years, having a total subscriber base of 951 Mn as of Mar' 2012 with 620 Mn urban (65%) and 331 Mn rural (35%) subscribers. India is the third largest network in the world after China and USA with a growth rate of 45% and has the highest growth rate in the world. This sector is primarily subdivided into two segments, which are Fixed Service Provider (FSPs) and Cellular Services. Telecom industry in India is specifically emphasizing on latest technologies like GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications), CDMA (Code Division Multiple Access), PMRTS (Public Mobile Radio Trunking Services), Fixed Line and WLL (Wireless Local Loop).

Till recently, the focus of organizations in India was the urban consumer, but now it is felt that with the tempo of development accelerating in rural India, coupled with increase in purchasing power, because of scientific agriculture, the changing life style and consumption pattern of villagers with increase in education, social mobility, improved means of transportations and communication and penetration of mass media have exposed rural India to the outside world and hence their outlook to life has also changed. Because of all these factors, rural India is now attracting more and more Organizations. The telecommunication is one of the fastest growing sectors and is the back-bone of the country for its growth. Tele-density has a positive correlation with the level of development of the region and it is of equally importance in rural and urban needs.

While the success so far was driven primarily by urban areas, the next phase of growth is expected to have a strong rural flavor. Today every fifth person in rural India is connected; from wage earners to shopkeepers, farmers to fishermen; mobile phones are helping in increasing their productivity. The mobile penetration Indian urban area is 169% while in rural is 39%, which make the rural segment more attractive to operators while having challenge to provide services in rural area.

In Rajasthan, which has been selected for this research purpose, constitutes of 25% of urban and 75% of rural population with a total population of 68.6 Mn as of 2011 census. It has a tele-density 73% overall and 145% urban and 37% in rural. Among all geography, Rajasthan has a

unique characteristic, which enforces the mobile operators to think and design a different strategy to get competitive advantage over others. This is mainly due to high spread, low population density, poor literacy rate and high operational cost for telecom operators.

Total 9 mobile service providers are providing their services in Rajasthan. The Customer Market Share (CMS) of each one of these is as follows:

About Idea Cellular Ltd., Rajasthan:

Idea Cellular Limited, Rajasthan Circle provides mobility services on GSM technology on Prepaid and Postpaid platform with value added services along with devices and Data card services. It provides Prepaid & Postpaid products and services through a wide range of Distributors (761 nos.) and Retailers (50,068 nos.).

It has total Subscriber base of 4.15 Mn with Rs. 748.6 Mn monthly revenue as of March'12 & FY 11-12 YTD revenue of Rs. 7152 Mn.

The business is facing addition challenges against its competitors:

- Low population per site (201 People/Sq Km against national average of 368 People/Sq Km), leading to incur higher cell site running operational cost.
- Sixth entrant in Rajasthan with no spectrum allocation in western Rajasthan (Jaisalmer, Barmer, Bikaner and Jodhpur districts).
- ~45% network population coverage while the coverage of Airtel & Vodafone is ~90%.

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With the continuous drop in call rates and tariffs with increase in competition and stringent pressures by Government regulations through TRAI made the telecom business more challenging. The margins are shrinking due to continuous increase in operational cost due to hike in Diesel price, distribution cost, customer service cost and government spectrum fee. The only way-out with the telecom operators for sustenance is to improve its process efficiencies and effectiveness through continuous improvement, innovation and exploring new areas of productivity improvement. The main business processes of telecommunication revolve around its distribution efficiency, product range, plan & tariff, network coverage & quality of customer service.

How Sales & Distribution operates in Idea Cellular:

Idea distribution channel normally contributes roughly 85-90 % of total business volumes which is prepaid business. The distribution comprises mainly of three entities:

1. A distributor; who has been assigned to serve the territory.
2. A distributor FOS (“Feet on Street”); who is appointed and paid by the distributor to service a particular area of his territory.
3. A Retailer; who purchases stock from the distributors through the FOS of his area and sells it to the end consumer.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The rural telecom distribution network faces challenge with respect to rate of increase of CMS. This results in adversely impacting the subscriber base in the area and other business KPIs in the region with depressing brand image.

“The CMS in rural towns of Rajasthan region is almost stagnant since last 6 quarters (from Oct’2010 to Mar’2012) which is 5.3% (average of the six quarters) against 9.8% in urban. The business of Idea Cellular from rural area contributes to 32% of overall business, which is ~240 Mn/ month.”

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The primary objectives of the study are:

1. To study and explore the factors impacting the rural telecom distribution towards increase in Customer Market Share (CMS).
2. To study, analyze and establish the gaps of the traditional rural telecom distribution in high spread geography.
3. To suggest factors and strategy to improve CMS in rural towns.

This research will also attempt to find out the reasons of less number of Distributors in rural area with high attrition and lack of interest in starting distributorship with their problems.

THE RELEVANCE OF THE REASEARCH

The relevance of the research in the current scenario is to differentiate the rural telecom distribution from urban, which is currently same. This research outcome could be used by other operators as well and which are of similar geography of Rajasthan. This research addresses the current distribution gaps and suggesting currently available Hub and Spoke model of distribution with additional factors which are relevant for telecom.

Earlier studies on distribution theory through this model do not focus on the various factors impacting telecom industry and also its impact on CMS was not established by any of such studies and researches.

The current study adds to the already existing research literature on the additional factors like how servicing in the value chain and distance factor impacts the CMS in rural towns.

SCOPE OF THIS RESEARCH

Scope of this paper is limited to 'Telecommunication sector' for its rural distribution and for prepaid telecom products. Also this study was conducted in Rajasthan region (Jodhpur, Udaipur,

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and Ganganagar) which is having high geographical spread and low population density, therefore factors identified in this study is restricted to similar geographical area only.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As per India Telecom 2009-10, KPMG & FICCI jointly suggested in ‘Key Challenges in Going Rural’ that despite the inherent attractiveness of the rural market, many operators have faced significant challenges in penetrating the market. Due to the many differences existing between the urban and rural markets, it is impossible to apply urban learning and Business models in a rural setup. Rural areas come with a completely different set of constraints and issues which the operators need to address in order to attract this fresh pool of customers. Operators face a number of challenges when it comes to the acquisition of rural customers. Although the cost of owning and using telecom equipment and services has come down considerably in the last few years, the typical rural consumer finds it hard to get its availability in the market as per his expectations & choice. This is attributed to the distribution issue in rural market of the telecom operator.

Yu An, Yu Zhang and Bo Zeng (May’11) evolved ‘The Reliable Hub-and-spoke design Problem: Models and Algorithms’ which is the hub-and-spoke system for distribution. It is a fully connected network with material/information flow between any two nodes being processed at a small number of critical nodes (i.e. hubs) and moved through inter-hub links. Compared with the one built with the point-to-point structure, it has a much smaller number of links. Also, because traffic flows are consolidated by hubs and inter-hub links, significantly less operating cost can be achieved because of economies of scale. Given such advantages, industry companies including airlines and logistics organization extensively use the hub-and-spoke architecture to reduce the operating costs.

Rural Telecom Business Model, suggested in Jan’ 06, that the distribution chain is not very well organized and requires a large number of intermediaries, which in turn increases the cost and creates administrative problems. Due to lack of proper infrastructure, manufacturers are reluctant to open outlets in these areas. They are mainly dependent on dealers, who are not easily available

for rural areas. This is a challenge to the marketers. It is well known that “Markets are created and not born”. The market so created should be tapped effectively.

As per Darrell Owen in 2005 in Community Telecom ‘A New Technical & Business Model’ the notion of telecenters has been one of the dominant forms of delivering access to ICTs in the more rural areas of developing countries. Unfortunately the experience gained over this last decade has proven that while the cyber café (a telecenter located in a more urban area) can generate sufficient revenues to be economically sustainable, with few exceptions those located in the more rural areas are typically only viable so long as donor funding continues to be provided and subsidize the costs of running these centers.

As per by Catalin Boja, Jul’2011, Clusters Models, Factors and Characteristics, suggested that in a hub-and-spoke cluster, describe in the fig-1, there are few dominant firms that represent the core of the cluster and are surrounded by numerous small firms that are linked directly to them. The most part of the cluster firms represent suppliers of raw materials, of externalized services or are specialized in a particular phase of the hub production process. The small firms trade directly with the large ones and depend on their client strategy. The hub firms define the relation inside the cluster and its dynamics.

Fig 1: Hub & Spoke Model

To address the issue of the urban and rural gap and reaching to the rural masses can be addressed by falling back on the Bottom of the Pyramid (BOP) marketing strategies as advocated by Prahalad (2004) and the 4 A's Availability, Affordability, Acceptability and Awareness (Anderson and Biliou, 2007, Kashyap and Raut, 2005). The BOP marketing strategies basically talk about aggregating the demand of consumers who have low individual purchasing power and are spread out. The basic commercial infrastructure suggested by Prahalad and Hart (2002) for

the bottom of the pyramid markets constitutes of four things, creating buying power, improving access, tailoring local solutions and shaping aspirations.

Anderson and Biliou, in 2007 suggested 4 As model described in Fig 2, is explained in the context of rural telecom. Each of the As is detailed out below. Availability the first A is about making the product reach the consumers and in the case of telecom services studies have shown this to be the biggest barrier to be overcome.

Fig 2: 4 A's Model

In the Journal of the Operations Research, Society of Japan, 2003, Vol. 46, No. 4, 409-428, On the Hub & Spoke model with Arc Capacity Constraint Mihiro Sasaki Masao Fukushima Nanzan explains the retail and distribution ecosystem change in the next few years and what will be the role of the independent retailers, operators and electronic items and handset manufacturers.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The theoretical framework was formulated on the basis of Hub & Spoke distribution model. This was developed to optimize the transportation cost with minimum time through distance and cost matrix with the objective to increase the market reach. In the current study, four more independent variables have been added for telecom sector, which are Covered population, Mobility penetration, Network Traffic and town distance from the base distributor town. The new model has been proposed, named 'Retailer as Distributor' – RAD model with the objective to growth and sustain the Customer Market Share (CMS).

The relationship between variables is established through regression analysis with weightage of each factor. Now, each factor is explained below with a hypothesis and this being tested for identifying relationship with CMS.

Covered Population

‘Covered population’ is the population count of the town, where the operator provides it network coverage with defined strength, so that subscriber can use the services effectively. It is the parameter which determines the potential of town and comparative assessment from its nearest competitor in the town.

The hypothesis which needs to be tested here is:

H1: There is impact of Covered population of the town on Customer Market Share (CMS) of the Mobile Service Operator.

Mobility Penetration:

Mobility penetration of the town is the ratio of total mobile subscribers in the town and total population of the town. This is irrespective of the operator’s coverage in the town.

H2: There is impact of Mobility penetration of the town on Customer Market Share (CMS) of the Mobile Service Operator.

Network Traffic:

It is the traffic a telecom site is getting through its usage in terms of ‘Erlangs’. One Erlang is defined as 60 Minutes of voice call usage on the site by one subscriber/ Or 60 subscribers use for 1 minute. It is calculated in two ways; i) Continuous basis in 24 hours (in a day) ii) Peak hour basis (Highest usage hour in the day). It is calculated to design the site capacity.

H3: There is impact of Network Traffic in the town on Customer Market Share (CMS) of the Mobile Service Operator.

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Town distance from the main distributor town:

It is the distance of the town, which is being serviced by the distributor base town in kilometers.

Due to economical aspects, the distributors could not be opened in each town with network coverage. Volume of business plays a significant role in financial survival of a distributor. Therefore a distributor covers more than one town. This main distributor serves the value chain (Retailers & Customers) to the nearby towns.

H4: There is impact of Town distance from the base distributor town on Customer Market Share (CMS) of the Mobile Service Operator.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE AND DATA COLLECTION

In the research study, a sample of 32 rural towns was selected from 3 zones of Rajasthan circle. The selection logic of these towns are based on the low Customer Market Share (4-6% CMS) compared to the circle CMS (which is 9.8% as of Mar'12) and uniformity with respect to coverage and launch date. Also the other factors with respect to the demography of these towns were similar.

The data of CMS and all the factors selected for the study are taken from secondary source, which is company's data base of Sales function. The monthly data was taken from Apr'11 to Dec'11 and average of the same was calculated for the analysis purpose.

LOCATIONS COVERED FOR STUDY

The locations (rural towns) selected for this study was selected based on the priority, where the organization is facing negative growth or stagnant with respect to CMS. The areas were from each zone (geography defined by the operator) of Rajasthan and are Ganganagar, Udaipur and Jodhpur.

Below 32 towns were selected from Ganganagar, Udaipur and Jodhpur zones for the study:

S. No.	Zone	Towns for study
1.	Ganganagar	Bhamatsar, Deshnokhe, Jangloo, Kakkoo, Jasrasar, Lalgargh, Palna, Panchoo, Saruda
2.	Udaipur	Amet, Banera, Bhim, Bijoliya, Ghatol, Jaloda, Karera, Karoi Kalan, Rishabhdev, Rundera, Singpur, Thamala,
3.	Jodhpur	Bagora, Bagri, Bilawas, Dangiyawas, Dhansa, Harjee, Panchori, Peelwa, Pipar City, Satheen, Siyana

MEASURES

Secondary data of these towns was collected from the organization with prior permission from Prepaid Sales Head. Also the validation of the data was done through clarifying the operational definition of each factor and sample data was validated through other source also.

S. No.	Factor	Unit of Measurement	Operational Definition	Data Source	Validation of Measurement system
1.	Customer Market Share (CMS)	Percentage	Total Subscriber base as of end of date of the month of Idea Cellular of the town/ Total Mobility Base of the town	COAI Report	Standard report from all operators
2.	Covered Population	Count in Numbers	Population of the town which is covered by the Idea Cellular network as of 31 Mar'11	GIS data	Standard report from Statistics Deptt., GOI
3.	Mobility Penetration	Percentage	Total mobile connections in the town/ Total population of the town	COAI Report	Standard report from all operators

S. No.	Factor	Unit of Measurement	Operational Definition	Data Source	Validation of Measurement system
4.	Network Traffic	Erlangs	Total network usage w.r.t Voice & Data of a particular site	BO report (Business Operations)	Automated System generated report
5.	Distance of serviced town from main distributor town	Kilometer	Distance travelled by road from one town to other by shortest available route	GIS data	Standard Data from Govt. of Rajasthan reported in web-site

RESEARCH DESIGN

This research was explorative in nature as the data that was already available with the organization. This study intended to conduct the research in the domestic market, specifically in Rajasthan rural region. Therefore data was collected from this region only. Secondary data for this study was collected from Apr'10-Dec'11. As all data type is continuous in nature, Regression analysis was used to identify the relationship between input and output variable. The R^2 value from regression equation arrived, which explains that the variation in input variables with output variable. The weightage and 'p' value for each factor calculated. Minitab version 14.0 was used to arrive at this statistical result. Detail of the analysis is available in the annexure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FINDINGS

The outcome of this research, which include exploration of factors, study and analysis shows that to each factor has an impact on Customer Market Share (CMS) in the rural town. But the factor,

which could be controlled, is 'the distance of the service town from the main distributor town' by designing new distribution system. This was further analyzed and identified that due to high distance (> 14 kilometers) from the main town, servicing of the retailers & customers could not happen. This resulted into lack of recommendation from retailers to customers and adverse brand image in the town. This was attributed to the low CMS in the town.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS RESULTS

Regression analysis was used to identify the relationship between input and output variable. The R^2 value from regression equation was arrived at 83%, which means that the input variables explain the variation in output variable significantly. It was found that, the 'distance factor' has the highest weightage (0.1347) and can be managed through a Hub & Spoke model. The outcome detail of the analysis is mentioned in Annexure-I.

SUGGESTION FOR SOLUTION

The solution suggested with the current constraint of low economy of scale, new distributors could not be opened in these rural towns. But a new channel needs to be introduced, so that it could bridge the service gap between main distributor to high distance town. Servicing of the town here means; collection of customer documents, regular replenishment of SIM & Recharge vouchers stock, open new outlets in the market, arrange for posters, danglers and other visuals at retail point. It would also support the retailers for resolution of payout and customer related issues.

This new channel was suggested as the 'main retailer' of the town, which is named as 'Retailer as Distributor' – RAD. This RAD will serve his own town retailers and the nearby town retailers and ensure servicing to them. There would a separate process for identification, selection, operation and support for these RADs. Below is the pictorial depiction of RAD model:

Fig 3: The proposed RAD (Retailer as Distributor) Model

A new economics was developed for this model, which help the business to increase the CMS in the market. As per the new model, the organization will additionally support the RAD financially for first 6 months and then it would become self sustained. (Details of economics & benefits of the model is mentioned in the Annexure II)

LIMITATIONS, ASSUMPTIONS AND SCOPE OF FURTHER RESEARCH

This research study was limited to rural town, where the distance between towns is high and for Telecommunication prepaid product. Also this study was not catered the primary data from the current distributors; who could have helped in identification of some new factors. These limitations would provide a new direction for further study.

The following assumptions have been made before developing this ‘Retailer as Distributor – RAD’ model:

- i. The RAD has basic business acumen and necessary knowledge to run the business.
- ii. The RAD has sufficient amount to invest in the business.
- iii. The RAD has fairly good relations in the market to run the business.

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